

‘Ayun adh-Dhib

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Also known as: Khirbat adh-Dhib, Khirbet el-Qureiye, MEGA-Jordan (#58869), MPS 79, TN13

Coordinates: [31.708949, 35.694336](#)

Periods Attested: Early Bronze, Early Bronze -> Early Bronze I, Early Bronze -> Early Bronze II, Early Bronze -> Early Bronze III, Iron Age, Iron Age -> Iron Age I, Iron Age -> Iron Age II, Iron Age -> Iron Age II -> Iron Age IIA

Introduction

The site of ‘Ayun adh-Dhib is located on the western edge of the Madaba Plateau in west-central Jordan, approximately 9 km west of the modern town of Madaba. The site is situated on a small spur overlooking a perennial spring within the Wadi adh-Dhib, an east-west oriented system leading toward the Dead Sea basin. Steep slopes descend from the site on three of its sides, with a narrow saddle connecting it to the hills of Fayha to its northeast. The site’s location appears to have been chosen in part due to the natural defensibility of the topography, but also due to the perennial spring located at the base of the wadi, approximately 250 meters west of the site.

The remains of a fortification or perimeter wall are visible surrounding the site, with the enclosed area measuring approximately 1 hectare. The surrounding artifact scatter extends the site’s footprint to about 3 hectares in area. Visible architectural remains include the aforementioned perimeter wall—appearing to likely be casemate in form—with additional intramural wall lines.

Material culture collected in archaeological surveys has identified two main periods of occupation: the Early Bronze Age I–III and a shorter occupation during the early Iron Age (Iron Age I–IIA). A small number of Roman, Byzantine, and Mamluk period pottery sherds were also collected, though these were limited in number and do not appear to evidence any significant activity at the site. Overall, ‘Ayun adh-Dhib presents a unique window into patterns of settlement and adaptation within an ecologically marginal zone on the western edge of the Jordanian plateau.

History of Excavation/Investigation

'Ayun adh-Dhib has seen only limited and intermittent scholarly attention over the past century. The earliest known recorded site visit was by Arnulf Kuschke of the Deutsche Evangelische Institut für Altertumswissenschaft des Heiligen Landes in the early 1960s, where Kuschke described the site under the local name Khirbet el-Qureiye, while noting surface material culture that included stone tools as well as Early Bronze and Iron Age pottery (Kushke 1961). Kuschke proposed a tentative identification of the site with the biblical Qiryaten/Qiriathaim mentioned in the Mesha Inscription (MI:10) and several biblical texts—a hypothesis later discussed by scholars such as Dearman and MacDonald (Dearman 1989: 176–177; MacDonald 2000: 122–123), though recent analyses have cast doubt on this association (Danielson et al. 2025: 34–35).

Figure 1. Site plan of 'Ayun adh-Dhib, courtesy of KMAP.

In the 1990s, Timothy Harrison included the site—then labeled Khirbat adh-Dhib—as Site 79 in the Madaba Plains Survey (Harrison 1997). Harrison reported that the site measured approximately 3 hectares and yielded substantial quantities of Early Bronze II–III pottery, along with some Iron Age pottery. Though the focus of the Madaba Plains Survey was on the Early Bronze Age, Harrison's survey confirmed the multi-period occupation of the site.

In 2011, the Department of Antiquities of Jordan formally registered the site to the MEGA-Jordan database as site #58869, under the name 'Ayun adh-Dhib, which is used in the present work.

In 2023, 'Ayun adh-Dhib was formally investigated by the Khirbat al-Mukhayyat Archaeological Project (KMAP). The KMAP team carried out a targeted survey of the site that included a surface collection, architectural mapping, and

preliminary ceramic analysis (Danielson et al. 2025). Focused on the Iron Age components of the site, this survey confirmed a fortified 1-hectare Iron Age settlement, possibly with casemate walls, and confirmed earlier identifications of an Early Bronze Age component of the site. Preliminary analysis of the early Iron Age ceramics (Iron Age I to early Iron Age IIA) indicates that they closely parallel the assemblages of the “Mujib-type” sites to the south and east, suggesting that the Iron Age component of the site relates to a broader pattern of non-urban, decentralized agropastoral communities in marginal ecological zones during the early Iron Age (Danielson et al. 2025: 38–42).

Figure 2. Selected Iron Age Pottery collected from 'Ayun adh-Dhib. See Danielson et al. 2025 (Fig. 3, Table 1), for further discussion.

Discussion

The significance of 'Ayun adh-Dhib during the Iron Age lies in its apparent association with a growing group of small, fortified and relatively short-lived sites dated to the 11th–10th centuries BCE in west-central Jordan. These “Mujib-type” or “Mudayna” sites as they have been called—distributed primarily around the Wadi al-Mujib, but now known to extend further north—reflect a decentralized, agro-pastoral mode of settlement that operated outside of state-level political frameworks (Porter 2013; Porter 2014; Porter et al. 2014; Routledge et al. 2014; Lev-tov et al. 2011; Klassen and Danielson 2023; Routledge and Halbertsma forthcoming). The 2023 KMAP survey of 'Ayun adh-Dhib revealed that the site character, location, architectural features, and material culture collected in surface surveys are consistent with this pattern of a small-scale, self-sufficient community.

Ceramic parallels with sites such as Khirbat al-Mudayna al-'Aliya and Hesban Strata 18–20 support the dating of the site to the Iron Age I and early Iron Age IIA, roughly the 11th–10th centuries BCE (Danielson et al. 2025). Similar to the pattern exemplified at other “Mujib-type” sites, the visible surface remains from 'Ayun adh-Dhib show no evidence for monumental public architecture, centralized storage, or other forms of administrative oversight. The extant remains, in comparison to other contemporary and similar sites, suggest that 'Ayun adh-Dhib functioned as a nucleated, autonomous community adapted to life within a marginal ecological zone. Its defensive location, fortifications, and access to a perennial water source suggest a focus on protection and self-sufficiency rather than relation to a central polity. The identification of 'Ayun adh-Dhib as matching the character of the “Mujib-type” sites extends the known geographic distribution of site pattern to the north and west, beyond the Wadi Zaqa Ma'in (Routledge and Halbertsma 2025) and onto the western edge of the Madaba Plateau.

The understanding of 'Ayun adh-Dhib during the Early Bronze Age is limited, though both the Madaba Plains Survey and 2023 KMAP Survey identified significant activity dated to this period. According to Harrison's analysis, and confirmed by KMAP, 'Ayun adh-Dhib (recorded as Site 79) produced diagnostic ceramics consistent with the Early Bronze Age I–III, and was estimated to cover about 3 hectares (1997: 29; Danielson et al. 2025: 36). In terms of 'Ayun adh-Dhib's relation to broader regional patterns during the Early Bronze Age, Harrison's (1997) analysis of the Madaba Plateau describes a pattern of small loosely clustered, spring-adjacent wadi sites during the Early Bronze Age I, shifting to an increase in the number and size of sites during the Early Bronze Age II–III. 'Ayun adh-Dhib follows this regional trend, though the exact duration or intensity of occupation during these phases of the Early Bronze Age remains poorly understood due to the limited surface data.

Nonetheless, the site's continuity of use—particularly during the early Iron Age—suggests a long-term recognition of the advantages of the location, including defensibility, access to water, and suitable land for cultivation and pasturage. As such, 'Ayun adh-Dhib offers a rare opportunity to examine how marginal upland environments were exploited across major chronological transitions, and how older landscape memories may have shaped later settlement choices. In sum, while formal excavations are necessary to refine our understanding of both the Early Bronze Age and Iron Age periods of activity at the site, 'Ayun adh-Dhib is already significant for illustrating long-term adaptive strategies in marginal ecological settings and for expanding our view of non-urban communities in both the Early Bronze and Iron Ages.

Cross Database Link

Levantine Ceramics Project: <https://www.levantineceramics.org/sites/3052-ayun-adh-dhib>

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